

ANALYSING PATIENT DATA OFF- PREMISES ON A NATIONAL SUPERCOMPUTER

Writing a Data Processing Agreement for the Googling the Cancer Genome Project

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Abstract

Whole genome sequencing (WGS) has become an integral part of clinical practices. Cancer patients can receive personalised treatment tailored to their unique genetic characteristics. Comparison between DNA derived from cancer cells and matched DNA from healthy cells using specific computer algorithms (callers) can identify variants specific to the tumour. These variants can then be used to understand why the cancer developed, monitor its progression and design targeted treatment strategies. Since human genomics data are classified as special personal data according to the new General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) of the EU, enabling these analyses, in particular when multiple institutions are involved, is challenging. This use case intends to provide guidance for the transfer and processing of patient WGS data across multiple scientific institutes with the aid of a Data Processing Agreement (DPA).

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What is important to remember before you start

1. Be aware that there are documents preceding the DPA and that you need to work with your institutional data security officer. One cannot shortcut to the DPA.
2. Check with your institution what templates of legal documents your organisation offers and who needs to sign them.
3. Take into account that certain processes (i.e. data requests and finalising a DPA between multiple parties) will take time. The better you are prepared the quicker you can conclude the necessary legal documents and start processing data.

Challenges of processing patient data off premises

Mutations in a patient's DNA can offer critical insights on how to treat the tumour. Specialized bioinformatic approaches are necessary to enable clinicians to analyse these data. In recent years, a set of algorithms (SV callers) have emerged aimed at finding cancer-associated structural variants in WGS data. However, as recent benchmarks show, comprehensive and accurate structural variants SV calling remains a challenge. Therefore, the '[Googling the Cancer Genome](#)' project (GTCG), a collaboration between the de Ridder group at University Medical Center in Utrecht and the Netherlands eScience Center in Amsterdam, has set out to create novel computational tools to improve on the detection of SVs in cancer genomes and their prioritization for clinical use.

In this use case we share the challenges associated with research data management (RDM) involving multiple stakeholders, our experiences to address those when analysing patient data using Machine Learning approaches and good practices of data stewardship.

As part of the GTCG project, we needed to process a large cancer WGS dataset that we requested from the Hartwig Medical Foundation (HMF). The dataset size and computational requirements prompted us to request resources on the Dutch national supercomputer ([Cartesius](#)). To process the HMF dataset on Cartesius, a set of agreements among the parties involved needed to be established.

Human genomics data are classified as special personal data according to the new General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) of the EU. Accordingly, human DNA sequence, which is unique to every human being (“fingerprint”), must be handled with care by adhering to standardised and legally approved Data Transfer and Data Processing Agreements (denoted as DTA and DPA, respectively). Additionally, one requires the Data Privacy Impact Assessment (DPIA) to identify potential risks in managing, sharing, and processing personal data and to define rules to prevent them. Finally, the Data Management Plan (DMP) includes the information above and regulates how all project members handle the data files across organizational boundaries, and ultimately, how the research outputs are published, shared, and archived.

Completing the DPA involves a **data controller** and a **data processor**. The controller is the party that collects and processes personal data and manages the further storing and processing of such. The processor is requesting data from a controller and can use and store the received data within the limitations that the controller has imposed. In the case of the GTCG project, the UMC Utrecht is the processor of data controlled by the Hartwig Medical Foundation (HMF). Defined by the DTA the GTCG project can process patient data on the supercomputer, which is arranged and confirmed by a DPA between the UMC Utrecht and SURF. The data steward interacts with controllers and processors to ensure the safe handling of legal documents and related data, which lead to the DPA between UMC Utrecht and SURF.

A data steward must ensure that all relevant documents and (standardised) processes are available to all stakeholders.

Use case:

Guiding the transfer and processing of patient WGS data (e.g. SV calling using the [sv-callers](#) workflow) between UMC Utrecht and SURF.

Project:

Googling The Cancer Genome: Identification and prioritization of relevant structural variations in whole genome sequencing data of cancer patients

Project Duration:

2017-2020

Partnering Institutions:

- Research partners: UMC Utrecht and the Netherlands eScience Center
- Provider of computing facility: SURF
- Provider of patient data: Hartwig Medical Foundation (HMF)
- Provider of legal support to finalise contracts: UMC Utrecht

Trigger:

The research partners want to transfer and process HMF patient data on Cartesius

Pre-condition:

- Legal documents such as the DPIA and DMP are required prior to establishing the Data Processing Agreement (DPA) between parties involved.
- DTA of the patient data provider must be signed by the research partners.
- Ensure GDPR-compliance when handling patient data by the research partners and the supercomputer facility.

Post-conditions:

- The received patient data can be transferred and processed on the supercomputer
- All parties are informed about data transfer and processing details according to the GDPR
- Legal documents are in place to protect the rights of all involved parties

Figure 1: Stakeholders interactions including administrative and legal documents over time.

1. **DMP** between the GTCG project partners.
2. **DPIA** between the GTCG project partners.
3. **HPC** usage agreement between the GTCG project partners and SURF to use Cartesius.
4. **DTA** for patient data between the GTCG project partners and HMF.
5. **DPA** between GTCG and SURF to process the data on Cartesius.

Data Processing Agreement & Responsible Data Management

In the GTCG project, the [sv-callers](#) workflow was developed to enable highly reproducible, scalable and portable SV calling with multiple callers in parallel on HPC environments. After a phase of successful testing on the institutional HPC, *sv-callers* was deployed to the supercomputer and executed on a large data set of cancer patients from the Hartwig Medical Foundation (HMF). The HMF assembled one of the largest data resources for metastatic cancer genomes in the world. We requested a dataset consisting of 100 tumor samples with a matched normal sample (25 TB in total) for two purposes: i) analyze the data using the workflow, and ii) compare/integrate the results with the Deep Learning-based approach also developed in the project.

At the beginning of the project, a data management plan (DMP) was written to identify and to define the project resources, workflows, and permissions of all project partners with regards to ownership, data storage and management, and research output dissemination. Based on the identified infrastructures, data flows, and data characteristics a data privacy impact assessment (DPIA) is conducted to identify possible risks, and to establish guidance how to mitigate or avoid these risks.

The next stage for this project was to request actual patient data from the Hartwig Medical Foundation (HMF). The application for this data access was supported by the information in the DMP and DPIA, which state the available data security and protection measures available at the data receiving institute - the UMC Utrecht. The data transfer agreement (DTA) from the HMF is a legally binding document that enables the UMC Utrecht to receive the requested data and allow a defined act of processing these data (i.e. analysing patient data on the institutionally internal HPC and later on the supercomputer). This was only possible with a Data Processing Agreement (DPA).

Figure 2: Processes and dependencies resulting in Data Processing Agreement.

Having these data privacy and management related processes in place enables the concise and efficient communication, data transfers and processing agreements with external parties in the future. We implemented good data management practises that assure the safe handling of highly sensitive patient data.

A step-by-step guide for DPA

Figure 3: Data Processing Agreement content and involved stakeholders.

With the new GDPR being in effect in May 2018, every institution had to adopt new rules and regulations, and to update/create new legal documents. In this regard, the GTCG project benefited from the previous project, [MinE](#), jointly carried out by the university medical centres (including UMC Utrecht), which established the DPA with SURF. By involving the divisional security officer at the UMC Utrecht early on, the project members could use the drafted DPA template for this request.

Having a data steward as part of the project team enables the scientific members to focus on research, while the data steward is concerned with managing the legal documents and interacting with the stakeholders.

1. Write a DMP and identify resources, ownership of research material and data, workflows and security measures ICT environments of all partners.
2. Find and connect to your institutional data security officer and complete a DPIA. Communicate the identified risks of handling sensitive data and the preventive measures required in the project.
3. Request compute resources from the (national) service provider (e.g. SURF regarding the Cartesius supercomputer) and sign a usage agreement.
4. Request patient data from the respective data controller (HMF in our case) and follow the procedures to obtain a signed DTA. Include the intended future use of the compute resource(s) in the data access application. Follow the defined means of secure data transfer.
5. Request help from your institutional data security officer (and perhaps legal support) on institutional DPA templates with external parties.
6. Adapt the institutional DPA template (e.g. UMC Utrecht) to the characteristics of your project and share this draft document with the data security officer of the intended party (e.g. SURF).
7. Sharing the DMP and DPIA of the project helps with transparency and trustworthiness of the requested data processing.
8. Finalise the DPA together with the external party and receive signatures from the authorised representatives of both institutions.
9. Store all documents (i.e. DMP, DPIA, DTA, and DPA) in a secure location that is accessible only by project members, e.g. a protected shared data storage of the project. The DTA and DPA are legally binding documents that protect both the data controller and the data processor.

Lessons learned

Luca Santuari & Arnold Kuzniar:

1. Take into account several months from requesting patient data (e.g. from HMF) to finalizing the DPA with all parties involved.
2. It greatly helps to have a dedicated data steward who coordinates the entire process.
3. Building on previous use cases can greatly facilitate the process for future applications (agreement between UMC Utrecht and SURF).
4. Following the steps, one can perform large-scale genome analyses that would take too long or simply would not be possible without the access to HPC resources available at SURF.

Jasmin Böhmer:

The sooner you find and connect to the relevant colleagues in your organisation, such as the data security officer, the more likely it is that you can benefit from previous experiences. In our case the prior involvement of our divisional data security officer with the MinE project and therefore SURF, helped us to draft the DPA quicker based on their approach.

Further reading

About the GTCG project:

1. eScience Center. 2020. Googling The Cancer Genome - eScience Center. [online] Available at: <https://www.esciencecenter.nl/projects/googling-the-cancer-genome> [Accessed 16 July 2020].
2. Medium. 2020. Teaching Machines To Recognize Cancer. [online] Available at: <https://blog.esciencecenter.nl/teaching-machines-to-recognize-cancer-420da40f547d> [Accessed 16 July 2020].

About the SV-callers workflow:

1. Kuzniar, A., Maassen, J., Verhoeven, S. and Santuari, L., 2017. Sv-Callers. [online] Research Software Directory. Available at: <https://www.research-software.nl/software/sv-callers> [Accessed 16 July 2020].
2. eScience center. 2020. Netherlands eScience Center Co-Develops Portable Workflow For Structural Variant Detection - eScience Center. [online] Available at: <https://www.esciencecenter.nl/news/netherlands-escience-center-co-develops-portable-workflow-for-structural-variant-detection/> [Accessed 16 July 2020].
3. Spaaks, J., Maassen, J. and Kuzniar, A., 2018. Portable HPC Workflows with Snakemake And Xenon. [online] Medium. Available at: <https://blog.esciencecenter.nl/portable-hpc-workflows-with-snakemake-and-xenon-e971e5127391> [Accessed 16 July 2020].
4. Kuzniar A, Maassen J, Verhoeven S, Santuari L, Shneider C, Kloosterman WP, de Ridder J. 2020. sv-callers: a highly portable parallel workflow for structural variant detection in whole-genome sequence data. PeerJ 8:e8214 <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.8214> [Accessed 16 July 2020].

About the Cartesius system:

1. Userinfo.surfsara.nl. 2020. Description Of The Cartesius System | Userinfo.Surfsara.Nl. [online] Available at: <https://userinfo.surfsara.nl/systems/cartesius/description> [Accessed 16 July 2020].
2. SURF.nl. 2020. Dutch National Supercomputer Cartesius. [online] Available at: <https://www.surf.nl/en/dutch-national-supercomputer-cartesius> [Accessed 16 July 2020].

About the MinE project:

1. SURF.nl. 2015. Graven In Een Genetische Goudmijn. [online] Available at: <https://www.surf.nl/graven-in-een-genetische-goudmijn> [Accessed 16 July 2020].

Read more:

1. Hara, K., Ohe, K., Kadowaki, T. et al. Establishment of a method of anonymization of DNA samples in genetic research. J Hum Genet 48, 327–330 (2003). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10038-003-0022-6> [Accessed 16 July 2020].
2. Kosugi, S., Momozawa, Y., Liu, X. et al. Comprehensive evaluation of structural variation detection algorithms for whole genome sequencing. Genome Biol 20, 117 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13059-019-1720-5> [Accessed 17 July 2020].
3. Cameron, D.L., Di Stefano, L. & Papenfuss, A.T. Comprehensive evaluation and characterisation of short read general-purpose structural variant calling software. Nat Commun 10, 3240 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-11146-4> [Accessed 17 July 2020].

Terms and glossary

ML - Machine Learning

Machine Learning is the study of computer algorithms that can learn to perform specific tasks automatically from data without being explicitly programmed. A good reference book is Trevor Hastie, Robert Tibshirani, and J. H. Friedman. *The Elements of Statistical Learning: Data Mining, Inference, and Prediction*. New York: Springer, 2009.

DL - Deep Learning

Deep Learning is a subset of Machine Learning algorithms that uses a multilayered graph of interconnected computational units called neurons (artificial neural networks) that are inspired by the structure of the visual cortex in the brain. Recently, these algorithms have achieved human-level performance in a wide variety of tasks, such as image classification, speech recognition and language translation. (See, for instance, LeCun, Y., Bengio, Y. & Hinton, G. Deep learning. *Nature* 521, 436–444 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature14539>). [Accessed 16 July 2020].

SV - Structural Variant

Structural Variants (SVs) are genomic regions in the DNA of an individual that differ in structure with respect to a reference DNA. They are commonly defined with a minimum length of 50 nucleotides to differentiate them from shorter insertions and deletions (INDELs). Examples of SVs include deletions, novel sequence insertions, duplications, inversions and translocations within a chromosome or between two chromosomes. SVs have been implicated in a wide range of diseases, including cancer. (See, for reference, Ho, S.S., Urban, A.E. & Mills, R.E. Structural variation in the sequencing era. *Nat Rev Genet* 21, 171–189 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41576-019-0180-9>). [Accessed 16 July 2020].

Sv-caller - Structure Variant Caller

A sv-caller is a computer algorithm aimed at finding and reporting Structural Variants (SV calls) in a genome using the information derived from sequencing the DNA in short fragments with high-throughput sequencing machines, such as those produced by [Illumina](#), and aligning the resulting sequences (reads) to a reference genome. (See, for reference, Cameron, D.L., Di Stefano, L. & Papenfuss, A.T. Comprehensive evaluation and characterisation of short read general-purpose structural variant calling software. *Nat Commun* 10, 3240 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-11146-4>). [Accessed 16 July 2020].

DPA - Data Processing Agreement

“A data processing agreement is a legally binding contract that states the rights and obligations of each party concerning the protection of personal data.”

Source: <https://gdpr.eu/what-is-data-processing-agreement/> [Accessed 16 July 2020].

DTA - Data Transfer Agreement

“Data Transfer Agreements (DTAs) are used to transfer human subject data from one institution to another for research purposes. A DTA is a contract between the providing and recipient institutions that governs the legal obligations and restrictions, as well as compliance with applicable laws and regulations, related to the transfer of such data between the parties.”

Source: http://www.ott.emory.edu/documents/forms/data_transfer_instructions.pdf [Accessed 16 July 2020].

DPIA - Data Privacy Impact Assessment

“A Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) is required under the GDPR any time you begin a new project that is likely to involve “a high risk” to other people’s personal information.”

Source: <https://gdpr.eu/data-protection-impact-assessment-template/> [Accessed 16 July 2020].

DMP - Data Management Plan

A Data Management Plan is a central document of project organisation and administration that helps to lay out and organise the resources and means of managing, storing, and sharing of data and material during the research phase. It also requires decision making on the publication and archiving of the research output in a FAIR data manner, including contributions to Open Science.

Read more: <https://www.scienceeurope.org/our-resources/implementing-research-data-management-policies-across-europe/> [Accessed 16 July 2020].

GDPR - General Data Protection Regulations of the European Union

From May 2018 the new GDPR is in place to protect and safeguard the personal and sensitive data of EU citizens. It introduced a set of principles that all data processors and data controllers have to follow, on top of revised data subject rights, as well as a framework of fines for data breaches.

Read more: <https://gdpr.eu/what-is-gdpr/> [Accessed 16 July 2020].

HMF - Hartwig Medical Foundation

“Hartwig Medical Foundation was founded in 2015 to enable systematic DNA analysis and to link genetic patient and treatment data on a national basis. This resulted in the first national database with genetic and clinical data of patients suffering from metastatic cancer in the Netherlands.”

Source: <https://www.hartwigmedicalfoundation.nl/en/about-hmf/> [Accessed 16 July 2020].

CPCT - Center for Personalized Cancer Treatment

“At the Center for Personalized Cancer Treatment (CPCT) doctors, researchers and many Dutch hospitals work together to find the best treatment for every patient.”

Source: <https://www.cpct.nl/> [Accessed 16 July 2020].

Pseudonymisation:

“Pseudonymisation means replacing any identifying characteristics of data with a pseudonym, i.e., a value which does not allow the person to be directly identified.”

Source: <https://www.health-ri.nl/anonymisation-and-pseudonymisation> [Accessed 16 July 2020].

Anonymisation:

“Anonymisation means processing data with the aim of irreversibly preventing the identification of the person to whom it relates.”

Source: <https://www.health-ri.nl/anonymisation-and-pseudonymisation> [Accessed 16 July 2020].

Pseudonymisation / Anonymisation for human genetic data:

“Genomic datasets that have been coded allow re-identification, even when they may be considered de-identified according to the HIPAA Privacy Rule, can nonetheless only be considered pseudonymised at best under the GDPR. Recital 26 states that pseudonymised data remain personal data.”

Source: <https://www.ga4gh.org/news/can-genomic-data-be-anonymised/> [Accessed 16 July 2020].

Data Steward:

An additional research support member in the team that takes care of interfacing with the other research support members of the organisation such as legal advisor, data protection officer, ICT managers. Main function is to implement, improve, and perform research data management related tasks on project, team, and organisational level.

Read more: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Data_steward [Accessed 16 July 2020].

UMC Utrecht:

“With approximately 12,000 employees, the University Medical Center Utrecht is one of the largest public health care institutions in the Netherlands and the largest employer in the region.”

Source: <https://www.umcutrecht.nl/en/over-ons/organisation> [Accessed 16 July 2020].

Netherlands eScience Center:

“The Netherlands eScience Center is the national center for the development and application of research software. Our software and tools enhance the use of digital methods in academic research, empowering researchers across all disciplines.”

Source: <https://www.esciencecenter.nl/about/> [Accessed 16 July 2020].

SURFsara:

“SURFsara is the centre of expertise for high-performance computing (HPC) services, data management and storage, cloud, e-science support and visualisation. SURFsara provides support for advanced research, in which (large-scale) data plays a major role, including services provided by SURFsara.”

Source: <https://www.surf.nl/en/the-surf-cooperative/surf-operating-companies> [Accessed 16 July 2020].

Cartesius:

“The Dutch National Supercomputer, Cartesius, is the flagship of SURFsara services. Cartesius is especially in high demand for its combination of fast processors and internal network, large storage capacity and the ability to process large datasets.”

Source: <https://www.surf.nl/en/dutch-national-supercomputer-cartesius> [Accessed 16 July 2020].

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